

Green Growth Meets Koopman: A Data-Driven Understanding of Economic Green Transitions in an Agent-Based Model

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Abstract

Human-induced climate change calls for transforming economies towards net zero carbon emissions while maintaining or increasing prosperity for all. Agent-based models have been increasingly used to study this type of complex socio-economic phenomenon. For a thorough understanding, agent-based models can be analysed as Markov processes, however, this is challenging for complex models. We borrow tools from molecular dynamics to obtain a coarse-grained description of the dynamics of an agent-based model that integrates a classic Ramsey growth model with two capital stocks and directed technical progress with opinion dynamics. Adapting the Molecular Kinetics via Topology framework to the agent-based setting, which uses an algorithm for identifying Invariant Subspaces of Koopman Operators with Artificial Neural Networks, we shift the view from a statistical analysis of simulation runs to a kinetic map that identifies macro-states and the main pathways between them. Kinetic maps for several scenarios of the opinion dynamics process reveal a “brown” and a “green” economy as macro-stable states, and allow for a comparison of the transition dynamics across scenarios. In particular, kinetic bottlenecks identified may inform targeted interventions.

1 Introduction

Transforming economies to net zero carbon emissions while maintaining or increasing prosperity for all is one of the greatest challenges of our time. There exist several economic policy efforts that aim to shift the economy to more sustainable pathways (3). One proposed solution among these is Green Growth (see, e.g. 12). The concept suggests economic growth while decreasing greenhouse gas emissions to protect the environment (33). However, in the Green Growth literature, theoretical foundations for understanding the underlying mechanisms to induce a transition from our current economic model to a carbon-neutral economy remain underdeveloped (35).

This paper is part of a line of research that aims to contribute to a theory of Green Growth by studying mechanisms that could underlie a green transition with the help of agent-based models (ABMs). ABMs enable the representation of economies as complex systems, with heterogeneous agents interacting in complex networks and embedded in a common environment, where both the networks and the environment may co-evolve with the agents’ actions. However, most ABM cannot be analytically “solved”, nor are they even formulated mathematically (16); results are obtained by investigating simulation output, which comes with challenges of its own kind (25), so that sometimes a system may not be as thoroughly understood as can be the case for the solution of an “equation-based model”.

The Agent-Based Ramsey growth model with brown and green capital (ABRam-BG) under study here was developed by (11) and directly builds on the model presented in (43) that adds three economic mechanisms to a strongly simplified Ramsey growth model structure: (i) technical progress through learning-by-doing, (ii) directed technical progress for a brown and a green capital stock, and (iii) a

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labour market with search. With these mechanisms, two equilibria are established in a setting with two time steps, present and future: a conventional business as usual equilibrium and a “green” equilibrium with lower emissions, higher growth and lower unemployment. This model is extended to a dynamically evolving ABM by (11). Adding social integration strategies (14), an opinion dynamics process becomes a potential driver of green transitions. A statistical analysis of the ABM simulations characterises the speed of the opinion dynamics process (indicating how fast agents change opinions) and the growth of the brown capital stock (accounting for when agents start investing in green capital) as the main indicators of a green transition. However, in spite of the ABM’s simplicity, a clear characterisation of green transition pathways remains intractable.

Several efforts have been made to construct analytically tractable models corresponding to ABMs to better understand the systems under investigation (for an overview, see 6). In particular, Markov process theory provides a powerful framework for characterising mathematically and analysing ABMs (19), either as Markov chains (19; 15; 1) or as continuous-time Markov jump process (44; 32). The Markov process perspective allows for studying the dynamics of the probability distributions governing the process. For simpler ABM, this enables e.g., the identification of absorbing states, basins of attraction, and invariant distributions, thus providing an analytical understanding beyond statistical insights from simulations.

Extending the Markov approach to more complex ABMs, however, poses challenges. Even when a Markov chain can be formulated for a given ABM, the chain’s structure may be too complex for a full analytical treatment (42). This calls for new frameworks that can handle this type of complexity and yet lead to analytical insights. We find such a framework in another field that handles high-dimensional systems with nonlinear and multiscale dynamics resulting from interactions of huge numbers of elements: molecular dynamics (34). In particular, we will use the Koopman operator for describing the system’s dynamics, a linear operator that can capture the nonlinear stochastic dynamics by shifting the focus to an evolution of functions. This approach is applicable when time-evolution data is available, but no simple mathematical description can be determined for the system (4) – as is often the case in molecular dynamics, and even more so for ABM. A straightforward idea then is to reduce the model’s dimensionality to construct a simpler Markov model in which the dynamics take place between a few macro-states. However, the resulting model may violate the Markov property (2) as through the projection of the dynamics into a reduced state space, conditional independence may be lost. The preservation of Markovianity can be guaranteed by using the ISOKANN (Invariant Subspaces of Koopman Operators with Artificial Neural Networks) algorithm (36). It is employed in the *MoKiTo* (Molecular Kinetics via Topology) framework proposed in (8) that provides a graph representation of the state space and highlights dominant pathways between macrostates of the system.

The present paper adapts this computational framework to agent-based models, thus naming the resulting method ABa-KiTo, and applies it to the above mentioned ABRam-BG model to illustrate how this data-driven method may help gain a better understanding of emergent transition phenomena in complex socio-economic and -ecological systems. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the ABM and the methods used, together with the required mathematical background. Section 3 describes the setting for the application before Section 4 presents and discusses results. Section 5 concludes.

2 Materials, Methods, and Theoretical Background

To provide all materials and methods together with their theoretical background, this section first introduces the ABM under study (Section 2.1), then provides a short recap on Markov processes and on the Koopman operator in Section 2.2, before turning to the MoKiTo framework in Section 2.3.

2.1 Material: The Agent-Based Model

The *Agent-Based Ramsey model with Brown and Green capital* (ABRam-BG) was developed to study opinion dynamics as a potential driver of green transitions and to illustrate their dynamics in a closed, decentralised economy populated by utility maximising agents with an environmental belief. ABRam-BG is available through the CoMSES Model Library (9), where the code and documentation according to the ODD protocol (16) can be found.

ABRam-BG describes a closed economy populated with n agents labelled by $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, and time steps are denoted by a subscript $t \in \mathbb{N}_0$. The agents are called farms because they combine economic activities usually attributed to firms (production) and to households (investment and consumption). Initially, farms hold brown capital $B_0^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ (high carbon intensity) or green capital $G_0^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ (low carbon intensity). In addition, they have an opinion $\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} \in \{0, 1\}$ about their environment that defines their investment behaviour. Agents who do not care about their environment ($\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} = 0$) hold and invest in brown capital and are called “brown farms” for simplicity. Analogously, agents who care ($\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} = 1$) hold and invest in green capital (“green farms”). The economic process in the model is deterministic and agents determine the amounts to invest and consume via an intertemporal utility optimization with two time steps, present and future. At the macro-level, a directed technical progress feedback loop represents learning by doing. In this setting, myopic agents lack incentives to invest in green capital. To include a forward-looking component, the model adopts a transitions research perspective, which views transitions as the outcomes of collective decisions, behaviour, and social interactions rather than purely economic factors (17). It hence introduces social integration strategies (14) that define cognitive and social algorithms designed to integrate information about beliefs and behaviours within social environments. At the agent-level, this is represented by a simple binary belief about their environmental responsibility, which then shapes their decision to invest in green or brown capital. The ABM evolves through a stochastic opinion dynamics process, in which brown farms may become “new green farms” that invest in green capital, but still use also their brown capital as it depreciates over time. Beliefs are updated randomly through standard opinion-dynamics¹ rules such as the Voter model or Majority rule (5).

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the ABM

The combined processes of opinion and economic dynamics result in a stochastically evolving ABM that may or may not reach a green transition in a specified amount of time, where we define an **economic green transition** as “when the economy’s green output reaches a share of 85% of the total output and does not fall back again”(23). The model’s process overview is illustrated by Figure 1, detail on its definitions can be found in A.

2.2 Mathematical background

For a short recap on Markov processes (Section 2.2.1) and to introduce the Koopman operator (Section 2.2.2), in all of the following, we denote $t \in \mathbb{T}$, where \mathbb{T} is a suitable index set; usually, $\mathbb{T} = \mathbb{R}_0^+$ or $\mathbb{T} = \mathbb{N}_0$, i.e., time is continuous or discrete. Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ denote a probability space, and let $(\mathbb{S}, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{S}))$ denote a measurable space where \mathbb{S} denotes the *state space*, $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{S})$ is the Borel σ -algebra on \mathbb{S} denoting the set of events, and $\mathbb{P} : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a probability measure on \mathcal{F} that assigns probabilities to events. We also assume that $(\mathbb{S}, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{S}))$ is a polish space, i.e. it is a separable, completely metrisable, topological space.

2.2.1 Markov process foundations

A Markov process is defined by a law of transitions between states described by a transition kernel.

¹As is customary in the opinion and belief dynamics literature, we also refer to beliefs as opinions.

Definition 1 (Transition Kernel (37)). We call the map

$$p : \mathbb{T} \times \mathbb{S} \times \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{S}) \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

a *transition kernel* or *transition function* if and only if the following hold:

1. $x \mapsto p(t, x, A)$ is a measurable function on \mathbb{S} , for each $t \in \mathbb{T}, A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{S})$.
2. $A \mapsto p(t, x, A)$ is a probability measure on $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{S})$, for each $t \in \mathbb{T}, x \in \mathbb{S}$.
3. $p(0, x, \mathbb{S} \setminus \{x\}) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{S}$.
4. p satisfies the Chapman-Kolmogorov equation for $t, s \in \mathbb{T}, x \in \mathbb{S}$ and for all $A \subset \mathbb{S}$

$$p(t + s, x, A) = \int_{\mathbb{S}} p(t, x, dz) p(s, z, A).$$

When properties (1) and (2) hold, we call p a *transition probability kernel* or *Markov transition function* (28, Chapter 3). Properties (3)-(4) define additional structures, making the transition function satisfy the semigroup property.

Definition 2 (Markov process). The stochastic process $(X_t : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{S})_{t \in \mathbb{T}}$ is called a *time-homogenous Markov process* with transition function $p : \mathbb{T} \times \mathbb{S} \times \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{S}) \rightarrow [0, 1]$, if for every $s \leq t \in \mathbb{T}, x \in \mathbb{S}$, and $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{S})$, we have

$$p(t, x, A) = \mathbb{P}[X_{s+t} \in A \mid X_s = x].$$

Note that $p(t, x, A)$ characterises the probability that the process moves from state x to a set A within time-span t . Moreover, the motion of the process to X_{s+t} depends only on the current state X_t ; this key characteristic for this type of a stochastic process is called the *Markov property* (21).

When the state space \mathbb{S} is discrete and we consider a unit time step, the transition kernel is a transition matrix with the elements

$$p_{xy} = \mathbb{P}[X_{t+1} = y \mid X_t = x] \quad x, y \in \mathbb{S}.$$

However, the uncountable state space of our ABM motivates the operator approach below.

Furthermore, if the transition probability kernel $p(t, x, C)$, where $C \subset \mathbb{S}$, is absolutely continuous with respect to a Lebesgue measure μ on \mathbb{S} , then there exists a *transition density function* $\kappa : \mathbb{T} \times \mathbb{S} \times \mathbb{S} \rightarrow [0, +\infty]$ such that

$$p(\tau, x, C) = \mathbb{P}[X_{t+\tau} \in C \mid X_t = a] = \int_C \kappa(\tau, a, c) \mu(dc),$$

where $\kappa(\tau, x, y)$ denotes the “probability” of the process to move from point a to the “target point” c within a lag time τ .

2.2.2 The Koopman operator

In this article, we use the *Koopman operator*, due to its key role in the the computational framework *MoKiTo* (Molecular Kinetics via Topology) (8). It is one of several transfer operators (22), i.e., a linear, bounded operator that describes the evolution of probability densities of a Markov process in the state space (37; 31). This perspective allows moving from the analysis of single trajectories – that may differ, not only through the system’s randomness, but also given their initial conditions and parameters – to an analysis of the flow of the system’s probability distribution (24). In particular, to use the Koopman operator we need observables of the system in form of functions. The Koopman operator describes the evolution of observables by representing the action induced by the system dynamics on functions. The benefit that the non-linear system dynamics can thus be studied using linear operators without sacrificing the system’s information comes at the cost of switching from considering an evolution in terms of points in the state space to considering evolutions of functions. The latter operator-theoretic picture lacks an immediate connection to physical intuition (4).

To address the drawbacks of working with an infinite-dimensional operator, spectral analysis of the operator is usually performed to gain insight into the dynamics of a system. Specifically, the analysis

of its eigenfunctions plays a key role, since by construction eigenfunctions span Koopman invariant subspaces (4; 20; 36).

More formally, the *Koopman operator* describes the evolution of observables $f : \mathbb{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ of the system, such that $f \in \mathbb{G}(\mathbb{S})$, where \mathbb{C} is referred as the output space, and $\mathbb{G}(\mathbb{S})$ is some function space over the state space \mathbb{S} .

Definition 3 (Koopman operator). *The Koopman operator for a lag time $\tau > 0$,*

$$\mathcal{K}_\tau : L^\infty(\mathbb{S}) \rightarrow L^\infty(\mathbb{S}),$$

describes the evolution of an observable $f \in L^\infty(\mathbb{S})$ and is given by

$$\tilde{f}(x) = (\mathcal{K}_\tau f)(x) = \int_{\mathbb{S}} \kappa(\tau, x, y) f(y) dy = \mathbb{E}[f(X_{t+\tau}) \mid X_t = x], \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbb{E}[f(X_{t+\tau}) \mid X_t = x]$ is the expectation value of the observable f at time $t + \tau$ starting in x at time t .

Note that integration is over all possible arrival points $y \in \mathbb{S}$ (7) and that we will consider time steps of $\tau = 1$ in the application. That is, instead of studying the dynamics of the system directly, we look at the evolution of observables defined on the system’s state space. Roughly speaking then, \mathcal{K} maps the observable function to the values it will take after the dynamics have progressed for one time step (20). The functions used can be interpreted as physically relevant observables arising naturally from the system, or as a set of basis functions for $\mathbb{G}(\mathbb{S})$.

Now, starting from the simplest case, for a constant observable, e.g. $\mathbb{1}$, we have

$$\mathcal{K}_\tau \mathbb{1} = \mathbb{1}.$$

Here, clearly, the information provided by the Koopman operator is not of any use, as the underlying system dynamics is irrelevant to the value of a constant observable. What we are interested in, however, are functions that change slowly with the system’s dynamics, as such functions provide information on these dynamics themselves. For example, if we have a function $\chi : \mathbb{S} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

$$\mathcal{K}_\tau \chi = \alpha \chi + \beta(1 - \chi), \quad (2)$$

with $\alpha \approx 1$ and $\beta \approx 0$, this function can be interpreted as the slowest observable of the system, since the system’s dynamics (in form of \mathcal{K}_τ) maps it “almost” to itself. Hence, if two states x and y have values $\chi(x)$ and $\chi(y)$ that differ greatly, then x and y are dynamically far apart: it is expected that trajectories from one to the other state are long, or in other words, the states will only very rarely be connected by a trajectory of the system in a short amount of time. However, states with similar χ values alone are not guaranteed to be dynamically close; they could lie on different pathways the system takes. For states to be dynamically close, in addition to having similar χ -values, they would need to be spatially close – a point we will come back to in the following section.

Since Equation (2) is not uniquely solvable, we use the ISOKANN algorithm (36; 38) that iteratively approximates the functions χ and $1 - \chi$ through a power-method-like eigenfunction computation while optimising for a high α value (Section 2.3.2). The resulting functions χ and $1 - \chi$ can be understood as fuzzy membership-functions: it indicates how much a micro-state belongs to the respective macro-states. The functions can further be used to construct an invariant dominant subspace of \mathcal{K}_τ because χ is the normalized counterpart of the dominant Koopman eigenfunction². This guarantees long-term consistency with the dynamics of the system, i.e. the projection of the original dynamics on this invariant subspace preserves the system’s Markov property (39). One of ISOKANN’s main benefits is that it avoids the difficult discretization of high-dimensional spaces.

2.3 Methods: The MoKiTo framework

As mentioned, we adapt the Molecular Kinetics via Topology framework (8) to ABM. This allows extracting kinetic information from a set of ABM simulations through Topological Data Analysis

²Eigenfunctions are solutions to the eigenproblem of the Koopman operator $\mathcal{K}_\tau \psi_i = \lambda_i \psi_i$. The eigenfunction ψ_0 associated with the eigenvalue $\lambda_0 = 1$ is called the constant first eigenfunction or the trivial eigenfunction, the first n_c remaining non-trivial eigenfunctions $\psi_1, \psi_2, \dots, \psi_{n_c}$ are the *dominant eigenfunctions* of the Koopman operator.

(TDA). The framework provides a graph representation of the state space of the system and highlights dominant pathways between macrostates, using the membership function χ associated to the ABM dynamics as ordering parameter. Using this framework involves three stages:

1. Exploration of system state space, see Section 2.3.1.
2. Construction of the χ -function with the ISOKANN algorithm, introduced in Section 2.3.2.
3. Clustering of simulation data filtered by the associated χ -function to obtain clusters of states that are dynamically close, i.e., not only in terms of χ -values but also spatially close. A second part of this step is an edge assignment to construct a graph representation which captures the system’s topological structure. The χ -function serves as ordering parameter that highlights the dominant kinetic pathways between macrostates in this graph.

Providing a structured view of the state space with macrostable states and transitions between them, the KiTo framework renders a kinetic picture of the system.

2.3.1 State space exploration

The goal of the state space exploration in the KiTo framework is to obtain a good coverage of the relevant state space for the Koopman operator-based analysis. In molecular dynamics simulations under typical ergodic settings, the dynamics tends to explore the entire relevant state space through long trajectories. In the case of ABM, we cannot assume this; trajectories depend on their initial conditions and parameters. Thus, for a full exploration of the state space, it makes sense to sample simulations starting from multiple initial conditions. This sampling strategy helps to ensure that ABA-KiTo receives enough diverse configurations to obtain a good description of the system’s macro-stable states and transitions between them.

2.3.2 ISOKANN: Invariant Subspaces of the Koopman Operator learned by a Neural Network

The ISOKANN algorithm can be described by three main ingredients, for details, see (40; 36):

1. A modified power iteration which solves the ISOKANN equation (2) and whose solution spans the dominant Koopman subspace.
2. A neural network approximation of the next χ iterate.
3. A Monte-Carlo simulation of the Koopman evaluation.

Power-shift scale iteration: ISOKANN iteratively finds eigenfunctions corresponding to the dominant eigenvalues of the Koopman operator. It is a fixed-point iteration based on the power method, also known as Von Mises iteration (29). In the original power method, for a given matrix A and an initial arbitrary vector ν_0 , the iterative computation

$$\nu_{n+1} = \frac{A\nu_n}{\|A\nu_n\|}$$

always converges to the eigenvector associated to the eigenvalue with the highest magnitude. In the case of the Koopman operator \mathcal{K}_τ , this is the constant first eigenfunction $\psi_0 = \mathbf{1}$. Thus, as discussed previously, this algorithm would not provide meaningful information.

The ISOKANN algorithm modifies the power method to

$$f_{n+1} = \mathcal{S}\mathcal{K}_\tau f_n \tag{3}$$

where the function \mathcal{S} is the linear transformation or the shift-scale function

$$\mathcal{S}\mathcal{K}_\tau f_n = \frac{\mathcal{K}_\tau f_n - \min(\mathcal{K}_\tau f_n)}{\|\mathcal{K}_\tau f_n - \min(\mathcal{K}_\tau f_n)\|_\infty}.$$

which prevents convergence against the trivial eigenfunction and guarantees that $f_n : \mathbb{S} \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

Neural Network representation: Although the Koopman operator is linear in the space of observables, the mapping from the raw ABM states to the invariant subspace is generally nonlinear. Neural Networks in ISOKANN are used to learn current basis functions $\chi^\theta(x_m)$ across multiple (potentially random) M training points x_m , where $m = 1, \dots, M$, such that:

$$\chi^{\theta_{n+1}}(x_m) \approx f_{n+1}(x_m). \quad (4)$$

The network parameters are updated by minimizing the mean-squared error between the network output and the approximated eigenfunction

$$L(\theta_{n+1}) = \sum_{m=1}^M \|\chi^{\theta_{n+1}}(x_m) - f_{n+1}(x_m)\|^2.$$

Monte Carlo approximation of the Koopman operator: To approximate the action of the Koopman operator in a given training point x_m , we use its representation as an expectation value

$$(\mathcal{K}_\tau f_n)(x_m) = \mathbb{E}[f_n(X_{n+\tau}) | X_n = x_m]$$

and approximate its action by the empirical average

$$\approx \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K f_n(X_{n+\tau} | X_n = x_m) \quad (5)$$

in a set of K trajectories. Then, the shift-scale function \mathcal{S} is applied to the resulting vector to form the approximated eigenfunction for the next iteration.

Given the high dimensionality of the system, we use the ISOKANN.jl package version 1.2.0 (38), which implements the core ISOKANN algorithm using neural networks.

2.3.3 Clustering and edge-assignment

MoKiTo is inspired by the Mapper algorithm. The Mapper algorithm is a topological data analysis technique that constructs a graph to represent and visualise the underlying structure of high dimensional data (41). In Mapper, a clustering algorithm is applied within intervals of the filter functions, in our case the χ -functions plays this role. Then the points are similar in the filter, as they fall in same interval of the χ -function, and close in their original metric state, since the clustering algorithm groups points within the interval based on their proximity. As the Mapper method does not depend on any particular clustering algorithm, several clustering algorithms may be used.

3 ABa-KiTo pipeline

To apply ABa-KiTo to the ABM sketched above, we establish that the ABM can be interpreted as a Markov process (Section 3.1) and lay out the settings to which the framework is applied (Section 3.2).

3.1 Interpretation as a high-dimensional Markov process

The first step in formulating ABRam-BG as a Markov process is the definition of the model’s state space. Given the opinion dynamics process, agents that change their opinion from not caring to caring invest in green capital while their brown capital depreciates. Consequently, this type of agent holds both types of capital and uses them for production. Thus, the state of agent i is given by

$$\mathbf{A} = (B^{(i)}, G^{(i)}, \mathcal{O}^{(i)}) \in \mathbb{R}^+ \times \mathbb{R}^+ \times \{0, 1\}.$$

Since the agent-based model is populated by n agents, the agents’ state space is given by

$$\mathbb{A} := \mathbb{R}^{2n} \times \{0, 1\}^n.$$

In the data-driven analysis below, instead of the capital stock values for the agents, their production values will be used, so that the algorithm does not need to learn also the deterministic relation between

capital and production. For the theoretical perspective of interpreting the ABM as a Markov chain, it does not matter which of the variables is used, as the production values can be deterministically computed from the capital stocks within each time-step.

At the system level, the n individual capital stocks aggregate into the total capitals, but the economic state of the system also contains the levels of brown and green technical progress β and γ , so that the economic state can be summarized as

$$\mathbf{W} = (B, G, \beta, \gamma) = \left(\sum_{j=1}^n B^{(j)}, \sum_{j=1}^n G^{(j)}, \beta, \gamma \right) \in \mathbb{R}^4.$$

Together, the ABM’s state space is given by the agents’ and the economic state space, formally

$$\mathbb{S} := \mathbb{R}^{2n+4} \times \{0, 1\}^n. \quad (6)$$

Note that the dimension of the agent-based model state space (6) is extremely large, due to the n agents and the additional aggregate variables.

Having defined the state space, the second step is to describe how the system evolves over time. Any future state of ABRam-BG, $\mathbf{S}_{t+1} = (\mathbf{A}_{t+1}, \mathbf{W}_{t+1}) \in \mathbb{S}$ is determined by applying the time-invariant updating rules sketched above and detailed in A to the current state \mathbf{S}_t , making the process Markovian,

$$\mathbb{P}[\mathbf{S}_{t+1} \mid \mathbf{S}_t, \mathbf{S}_{t-1}, \dots, \mathbf{S}_0] = \mathbb{P}[\mathbf{S}_{t+1} \mid \mathbf{S}_t]. \quad (7)$$

That is, the evolution of the system depends only on the present state and does not require knowledge of past states (21).

3.2 Simulation Setting

An ABRam-BG simulation is defined by three components: (i) a set of fixed parameters, (ii) a configuration that determines the social structure in which agents interact, and (iii) a set of initial conditions used as starting points for simulations. We fix (i) throughout all simulations to keep the underlying dynamics consistent for exploring the state space, see (Table 1).

Table 1: Fixed parameters for the ABM simulations

Parameter	Name	Value
n	Number of farms	100
t	Length of the trajectory in time steps	50
S	Sample size per initial condition	400
K_0	Initial total capital	10
α	Output elasticity of capital	0.33
δ	Capital depreciation rate	0.05
ρ	Factor to discount future felicity	0.99
$K_0^{(i)}$	Farms initial capital	0.1

Initial conditions in (iii) concern the values assigned at time step $t = 0$ to the technical progress levels and the total green and brown capital stocks, which in turn determines how many green and brown agents there are initially. For practical implementation, we express these conditions through a simple measure: the initial green-to-brown ratio r_g . This ratio jointly sets the initial ratio of technical progress $r_g = \frac{\gamma_0}{\beta_0}$ and the proportion of total green and brown capital stocks, i.e. $G_0 = r_g K_0$ and $B_0 = (1 - r_g) K_0$. In the experiments, we use the following green-to-brown ratios

$$r_g = \{0.05, 0.07, 0.10, 0.12, 0.15, 0.20, 0.25, 0.30, 0.35, 0.40\},$$

to cover the region of the state space that we are interested in studying.

To highlight the role of the network between agents in the opinion dynamics process for the occurrence of a green transition, in the following, we define three scenarios for this process, i.e., we vary (ii) between the scenarios. We are then interested in whether and how the system reaches an economic

green transition, i.e., a green output share of 85% of the total output (23). Formally, the economy’s **green output share** is given by

$$R_t = \frac{P_{G_t}}{P_{G_t} + P_{B_t}}, \quad (8)$$

where $P_{G_t} = \sum_{j=1}^n P_{G_t}^{(j)}$ and $P_{B_t} = \sum_{j=1}^n P_{B_t}^{(j)}$ are the total green and brown production of the economy at time t .

3.2.1 Scenario 1

As detailed in (11), using a fully connected network, the probability that agents switch to green, which is conditional on the number of green agents in the system, can be fully characterised. We therefore use the fully connected case as the baseline scenario. As increasing the number of agents interacting

Table 2: Configuration for Scenario 1

Parameter	Name	Value
OD	Opinion dynamics	Voter dynamics
\mathcal{N}	Network topology	Fully-connected
ℓ_{FC}	Number of interacting farms per time step	3

in the opinion dynamics process per time step rescales the transition dynamics, we fix this number to 3 agents per time step. They interact through a voter dynamics (Table 2).

We use confidence intervals (CI) to determine the number of runs needed so that the estimated proportion of successful green transition is a reliable representation of the underlying probability in the model. Specifically, we select 400 runs per initial conditions to ensure that the 95% CI for the proportion of successful green transitions remains below a 10% CI length as recommended in (18), see Figure 2. To compute the 95% CI for the proportions of successful green transitions, we use

Figure 2: Proportion of simulation runs leading to a green transition against the initial green-to-brown ratio for a sample size of 400 runs. Error bars indicate the length of the 95% Clopper-Pearson CI.

the Clopper-Pearson exact method, rather than the classical (Wald) approximation, as the classical method is inadequate in our context given that green transitions are rare events at least for small brown-to-green ratios, and the observed proportions may be very small or zero (26).

3.2.2 Scenarios 2 and 3: Varying Network Topology and Opinion Dynamics

For a controlled comparison of whether and how the kinetic map of the ABM varies under different dynamics and network topology, we define two further scenarios with a voter dynamics in a small-world network with three interacting agents, and a majority rule with group size of 5 agents, see Table 3.

Figure 3 displays the proportions of simulations that lead to a green transition for these two model configurations.

Table 3: Configurations Scenario 2 and 3

Parameter	Name	Value
OD	Opinion dynamics	Voter dynamics
\mathcal{N}	Network topology	Small-World
$f_{SW}^{(i)}$	Neighbours number of farm i in a small world network	5
ℓ_{SW}	Number of interacting farms per time step	3
OD	Opinion dynamics	Majority rule
ℓ_{MR}	Group size for Majority rule	5

(a) Voter dynamics, small world-network

(b) Majority rule with group size 5

Figure 3: Proportion of simulations runs leading to a green transition against the initial green-to-brown ratio for a sample size of 400 runs, under (3a) Scenario 2 and (3b) Scenario 3, error bars as in Figure 2.

3.3 Configuration of the clustering algorithm

We choose HDBSCAN (Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Application with Noise), a density-based hierarchical clustering algorithm (27). HDBSCAN does not require prespecifying the number of clusters and can identify clusters of varying shapes, sizes and densities. We select this algorithm primarily because the ABM trajectories sample different regions with non-uniform frequency (Figures 8 and 12) and HDBSCAN’s adaptive density thresholds handle this heterogeneity. Moreover, the number of metastable states is unknown a priori.

To accommodate heterogeneous density and size distributions across intervals, we implement an adaptive parameter scaling as described in Table 4. Within each interval i , HDBSCAN clustering parameters are adapted based on the interval size I_i and the normalised density ρ_i .

Table 4: HDBSCAN Clustering Configuration

Component	Implementation
Base parameters	min_cluster_size=50 min_samples=8
Adaptive scaling	Size: $\sqrt{I_i}/60k \in [0.9, 1.15]$ Density: $1/\rho_i \in [0.95, 1.05]$
Selection method	‘eom’ ($I_i \geq 15k$), ‘leaf’ ($n_i < 15k$)
Fallback (no clusters)	Reduce thresholds by 20-25% Override to ‘eom’ if $I_i > 30k$
Noise reduction	92nd percentile k-NN reassignment

To determine the connection between clusters, we use MoKiTo’s adjacency matrix-construction module, which identifies edges between clusters using a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) classifier with 100 hidden units trained on cluster labels. Two clusters are considered connected if the classifier assigns ≥ 10 trajectory points near the cluster boundary to the neighbouring cluster, indicating sufficient overlap for transition feasibility. The resulting adjacency matrix defines a directed graph constructed using MoKiTo’s BuildGraph class, capturing the feasible transition pathways between metastable states.

4 Results and Discussion

Results of applying the ABa-KiTo pipeline to the data generated by ABRam-BG are presented for the scenarios described in Section 3.2 according to the three phases of ABa-KiTo, starting with the baseline Scenario 1 (Section 4.1) and then comparing with the other two scenarios in Section 4.2.

4.1 Scenario 1

Recall that the configuration in this scenario is a voter dynamics in a fully connected network with 3 interacting agents.

4.1.1 Exploring the state space: analysis of the ABM trajectories

The state space exploration is based on a set of 4000 ABM trajectories obtained under the fixed parameters of Table 1 for the initial conditions specified in Section 3.2. Trajectories of the green output share, that indicates a green transition if it reaches 85% or more, are illustrated in different forms in Figure 4. Single trajectories run as examples for each initial condition (Figure 4a) indicate that the initial green-to-brown ratio but also stochastic variability play key roles in the occurrence of a green transition: a higher green-to-brown ratio is not always connected to an earlier green transition. For example, the economy with an initial green-to-brown ratio of 0.2 (brown line) here experiences a faster transition than economies with higher ratios of 0.25 (pink line), 0.3 (gray line) and 0.35 (light green line).

Figure 4: Green output share in (4a) example trajectories per initial condition where the dotted black line indicates a carbon lock-in (green output share below 15%), while the dashed black line indicates a green transition (green output share above 85%), and (4b) in bundles, as well as against the number of green agents (4c).

The extended time frame in this case shows that some transitions occur after the 50 time steps window used in the ABa-KiTo pipeline below. In fact, as brown farms can turn green but green farms cannot turn back, in the long run, a green transition is bound to occur. However, in terms of policy, only those green transitions within some specified time frame are of interest.

Following the statistical analysis from (11), we compute the average consensus rate per trajectory, i.e.

$$\frac{X_t - X_{t-1}}{X_{t-1}} \times 100\%,$$

where X_t and X_{t-1} are the random number of green farms at time steps t and $t - 1$, and the mean consensus rate is the average of these values over the 50-time steps length of the trajectory. Plotting this rate against the average brown capital growth rate per trajectory reveals that the occurrence of a green transition is an interplay between how fast agents switch to green (consensus rate) and when they do so (brown capital growth rate), see Figure 5. The brown capital growth rate is used here instead of using the green capital growth rate, as the latter indicator exhibits substantial stochastic variability across trajectories, which makes identifying consistent patterns difficult.

To recap some of the analysis from (11), we use the Gross Domestic Product (GDP or Total production) to evaluate the economic dimension of the model and the economy’s CO_2 emissions for the environmental dimension (Figure 6). The economies with higher green-to-brown ratios and hence earlier green transitions exhibit the lowest CO_2 emissions (Figure 6a). They also generally show lower GDP as green capital is initially less productive than brown capital (Figure 6b). However, a finding

Figure 5: Mean consensus rate against mean brown capital growth rate per trajectory with initial green-to-brown ratio of 0.1 (in 5a), 0.25 (in 5b), and 0.40 (in 5c).

Figure 6: ABM simulation output of (6a) CO_2 emissions, and (6b) Gross Domestic Product (GDP) across different initial conditions for voter dynamics in a fully connected network with 3 interacting agents.

from (11) is confirmed by the already mentioned early transition case (brown line): with an earlier green transition, the economic dynamics can catch up, leading to benefits in terms of both higher GDP and lower CO_2 emissions, making a case for green growth (for details, see 11).

The analysis of trajectories indicates general characteristics of the system, but does not give deeper insight into its working, limiting explanatory power for the emergence of green transitions. Therefore, the ABa-KiTo framework will be used to provide a kinetic picture of the system next.

4.1.2 ISOKANN to determine the χ -function of the ABM

To approximate the χ -function that encodes the slow dynamics of the agent-based model, we use ISOKANN.jl version 1.2.0. The algorithm requires two arrays, a vector $X_s \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$ of starting points, and a tensor $Y_s \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N_{\text{koop}} \times M}$ of propagated points. Here N is the size of the ABM state, M is the total number of time steps, which are referred to as time frames in the context of this algorithm, and N_{koop} is the number of Koopman-samples per starting point.

For training the neural network, we feed it with states of size $N = 202$ (100 agents with two types of production $P_{G_t}^{(i)}$ and $P_{B_t}^{(i)}$, the total number of green agents X_t and the green output share R_t). As the experiment is run for 10 initial conditions, with a sample size of 400 simulations for trajectories of 50 time steps, the total number of time frames is $M = 50 \times 400 \times 10 = 200000$. Thus, we have $X_s = (202, 200000)$ starting points and $Y_s = (202, 1, 200000)$ propagated points. The number of Koopman-samples per starting point $N_{\text{koop}} = 1$, since we work with given time series from the ABM simulations. The resulting learned χ -values are displayed in Figure 7a, where we plot the macro variables against time and we colour with their associated χ -value (Figure 7b).

We clearly observe two macro-states: a brown economy ($\chi \approx 0$), coloured by red with low numbers of green farms and green output share, and a green one ($\chi \approx 1$), coloured accordingly with high numbers of green farms and green output share. States coloured orange-yellow-light-green correspond to transition states between the brown and green macrostates, they have positive fuzzy membership values in both the brown and the green macro-state. While the brown and green economy macro-states could also be intuitively grasped in the statistical analysis, the χ -function now allows quantifying how

Figure 7: Scatter plots of (7a) χ -values and their associated time frame and (7b) the total number of green agents, green output share and time coloured by their corresponding χ -value.

much a transition state belongs to a brown or a green economy. Clearly, states coloured by red and green are dynamically far away; a further analysis of transition states that are dynamically close will follow in Section 4.1.3.

The χ -function can also be used to identify which macro variables of the ABM are good indicators of the system’s dynamics, via a correlation analysis. This was carried out using a second data set of ABM simulations (B). Table 5 shows a pattern of high correlation of the χ -values with the green variables. The correlation is highest for the total number of green agents, followed by the green output share. These findings suggest that the model’s green macro-variables play a key role in the emergence of transitions while in the statistical analysis these variables could not be used due to their stochastic nature, and the indirect, brown variables were used instead.

Table 5: Correlation analysis of the χ -function with macro variables of the ABM with Voter Dynamics on a fully connected network

Variable	Spearman	MI-KDE
Total number of green farms	0.763	0.470
Green Output Share	0.679	0.394
Green Capital Share	0.632	0.352
Total Green Production	0.136	0.000
Total Green Capital stock	0.128	0.000
Green Technical progress	0.111	0.000
Total Capital	0.073	0.000
Total Brown Capital	0.068	0.000
Total Production (GDP)	0.059	0.000
Brown Technical progress	0.054	0.000
Total Brown Production	0.053	0.000

4.1.3 A kinetic map of the ABM

To construct the kinetic map, i.e. a coarse grained representation of the state space and the main pathways between macrostates, we use the MoKiTo modules and modify them according to the constraints of our data. For an informed decision on the number of intervals to subdivide the learned χ -function, we plot a histogram (Figure 8). Based on this, we use $i = 4$ disjoint intervals containing states with similar χ -value. We use k-means clustering, to balance the interval sizes for memory management, given the uneven distribution of the χ values which were heavily concentrated near $\chi \approx 0$ (Figure 8).

We find 95561, 70989, 25485, and 7965 states for the intervals, respectively. For each time frame

Figure 8: Distribution of χ -values with interval boundaries

k , we have the vector state:

$$S_k = \left(\left((P_B^{(j)}, P_G^{(j)})_k \right)_{j=0}^{n=100}, X_k, R_k \right).$$

Then, we find the clusters of states that are dynamically close, meaning both spatially close and close in terms of similar χ -values. We apply the HDBSCAN clustering algorithm in each of the intervals.

For interpreting the idea of dynamically close states in our data, we plot the two macro-variables most correlated with χ against time and colour them according to clusters (Figure 9a). This plot provides an overview, but more detail can be seen when constructing a graph that captures directly the topological structure of the high-dimensional data (Figure 9b).

(a) Macro trajectories

(b) Kinetic map Scenario 1

Figure 9: (9a) Scatter plot of the total number of green agents and green output share against time, coloured according to clusters, and (9b) graph of the kinetics. Each node is coloured by cluster, labelled by its average χ -value, node size indicates cluster size, and the size of the edges indicates the number of transitions between nodes, red arrows indicate the main path between macro-states.

Using MoKiTo's modules for the graph requires constructing a count and adjacency matrix. The resulting graph encodes the system's coarse-grained dynamics, where the nodes represent metastable states. To set the size of the edges between nodes, we use the count matrix that indicates how many transitions occur between two nodes in the data, thus indicating how the system moves between states. This structured view of the system is a *kinetic map*.

Additionally, using a modified version of MoKiTo's Find Paths module, we identify the main transition path that maximises the sum of transition counts; marked by the red arrows in Figure 9b. This path is the most frequently travelled route through the state space, but it is not necessarily the

fastest among the alternative routes. In particular, it passes through the cyan node, a transition state with average $\hat{\chi}$ -value of 0.419, and with thin outgoing edges, meaning that the transition to the next state along the path is relatively rare. The main path likely captures the aggregate behaviour across the set of trajectories while alternative paths capture transitions where timing and initial conditions align for rapid green transitions.

To further analyse which macro-states play an important role in green transition dynamics, we exploit the graph structure of the kinetic map using the well-known betweenness centrality measures from graph theory. This measure counts how many shortest paths between all pairs of nodes pass

Figure 10: Betweenness centrality measure of the kinetic map for Scenario 1.

through a given node (30). A node with high betweenness centrality lies on many paths connecting different regions of the state space. Figure 10 colours the graph according to this measure, showing that the main path passes through two nodes with high betweenness centrality. These nodes are topologically critical for connecting states. Specially, the transition state with average χ -value of 0.419 (cyan node in Figure 9b), with the highest betweenness centrality, is essential for connecting macrostates.

Its outgoing edges are relatively thin and few in comparison with the thicker ingoing edges, indicating that the outgoing transitions are more rare. Paths continue primarily to the node at $\hat{\chi} = 0.827$, but there is another much tinier edge to $\hat{\chi} = 0.428$ that corresponds to a rare alternate outcome. This latter node is a rarely visited macrostate that represents endpoints of a pathway where no further transitions occur, at least with a time horizon of 50 steps. In the longer run, as already discussed, it is known from the model’s theory that a green transition is inevitable. The combination of high betweenness centrality and low transition frequency identifies the cyan node as a kinetic bottleneck in the system. Such bottlenecks in the state space can be interpreted as regions with high socio-economic barriers in green transition dynamics.

4.2 Kinetic Map variations: Scenarios 2 and 3

We now apply ABa-KiTo to simulation data from the ABRam-BG configurations defined as Scenarios 2 and 3: Voter dynamics in a small-world network with three interacting agents, and Majority rule with group size 5, respectively (for details see Table 3). For a controlled comparison, parameters (Table 1) and initial conditions remain unchanged.

The different ABRam-BG configurations sample different regions of the state space (11), leading to different distributions of the χ -function (Figure 12). Changing the network topology from fully connected (baseline) to a small-world network in Scenario 2 decreases the number of green transitions (Figure 3a): there are less states associated with $\chi \approx 1$ (Figure 12a). Consequently, this configuration samples a smaller region of the state space (Figure 11a). In comparison, switching to the majority rule in Scenario 3 increases the proportion of economic green transitions per initial condition (Figure 3b); there are more states with $\chi \approx 1$ (Figure 12b), hence, a larger region of the state space is sampled by this ABM configuration (Figure 11b).

Figure 11: Scatter plots of the total number of green agents, green output share and time coloured by χ -value for (11a) scenario 2 and (11b) scenario 3.

Figure 12: Distribution of χ -values with interval boundaries for (12a) scenario 2, and (12b) scenario 3.

Table 6: Number of initial states assigned to each interval prior to clustering for Scenarios 2 and 3.

ABM configurations	Number of states per interval		
	N = 1	N = 2	N = 3
Voter dynamics in small-world network	112868	73387	13745
Majority rule	141764	50138	8098

Given the distribution of learned chi values (Figure 12), we divide the χ -function into $i = 3$ intervals using k-means clustering. The number of states per interval are given in Table 6. Following the same steps as for the baseline Scenario 1, the analogous results are illustrated in Figures 13 and 14.

The most striking result to emerge from the kinetic maps is how much the structures differ – an information that is quite invisible when looking at trajectories only. For Scenario 2 the node with the highest average χ has a value of 0.690 but is small (light pink node). The simulation data frequently exhibits dynamics associated to the node with average $\chi = 0.348$ (yellow node), corresponding to a transition region. This node’s multiple tiny outgoing edges suggests a fragmented transition region. This likely arises from limited sampling of the state space and clustering artifacts, rather than representing separate macrostates, given the similar average $\hat{\chi}$ -values of the nodes, similar edge patterns, and close to zero betweenness centrality of the smaller nodes (Figure 14a).

On the other hand, Scenario 3 displays a more unified transition region, consisting of only two nodes (yellow with $\hat{\chi} = 0.269$ and blue with $\hat{\chi} = 0.316$, Figure 13f), both of which also have the highest betweenness centrality in the graph (Figure 14b). Moreover, the most probable path passes through the larger of these two nodes, highlighting its role as a kinetic bottleneck. Outgoing edges from this node to the other nodes are thin, indicating that transitions into the green state are relatively rare. However, the edge along the most probable path to the green node at $\hat{\chi} = 0.861$ is thicker than the others, confirming it as the primary route. Outgoing from the green state, the fine fragmentation into multiple nodes ($\hat{\chi} = 0.836, 0.856, 0.861$) appears to reflect clustering artifacts or local macro-dynamics, as suggested by their low betweenness centrality values and close average $\hat{\chi}$ -values.

Scenario 2

Scenario 3

Figure 13: Scenario 2 and 3: number of green agents and green output share trajectories (13a, respectively 13d), scatter plots coloured by clusters (13b, 13e) and kinetic maps (13c, 13f).

A comparison of all three scenarios reveals consistent patterns across them, such as similar dominant pathways, transition states that act as kinetic bottlenecks, and alternative and faster paths between macrostates. While Scenario 1 provides a relatively balanced view of the system’s kinetics, the other two scenarios show a more fragmented graph. It is worth noting that there also are differences in the graphs in the betweenness centrality measure, where Scenario 1 exhibits the highest measure (max. 0.5, Figure 10) and it decreases in the other cases to about max. 0.35 and max. 0.15 respectively, Figure 14. This suggests that changing the type of interactions, i.e., to changes how agents process and aggregate information in their decision-making, could lower or increase socio-economic barriers. As in the majority rule case, where increasing the use of information aggregation by agents, lower these barriers.

Further research is required to evaluate the impact of different social integration strategies in the green transition dynamics. Another possible investigation could combine trajectories from all three ABM configurations to yield a kinetic map with broader coverage of the state space. Due to computational constraints, we did not perform this combined analysis here, and leave it for future research.

5 Conclusions and outlook

Agent-based models (ABMs) often can be interpreted as high-dimensional Markov processes, but their nonlinear and multiscale dynamics may make direct analysis of state transitions intractable. To obtain a reduced yet Markovian representation that provides an understanding of a system’s dynamics beyond what can be learned from statistical analysis of simulation runs, this paper adapted and applied a method from molecular dynamics to analyse emergent kinetic behaviour in the ABM.

Figure 14: Scenario 2 and 3: Graph coloured according to betweenness centrality.

The ABa-KiTo method, based on the MoKiTo framework (Molecular Kinetics via Topology) provides a coarse grained description of the agent-based dynamics that does not explicitly discretise the state space and preserves the Markov property of the system. The method extracts an order parameter χ that describes slow dynamics in the agent-based model. As a membership function of subregions of the state space, the χ -function reflects macro-states in the dynamics, and a correlation analysis identifies those variables that best describe the process. χ is learned with ISOKANN, an algorithm trained with a set of ABM trajectories, where the key requirement is that trajectories sample a broad region of the state space. In addition, topological data identifies dominant pathways between the macro-states to construct a kinetic map of the system.

ABa-KiTo is applied to a highly stylised ABM that couples economic and opinion dynamics reconciling short-term utility maximisation with longer-term environmental considerations for studying green transitions as emergent phenomena arising from micro-level social and economic interactions. The resulting kinetic maps of the ABM confirm two dominant macro-states: a brown ($\chi \approx 0$) and a green economy ($\chi \approx 1$). It is in the transition dynamics where differences between scenarios with varying opinion dynamics processes (changing network topology or interaction structures) arise. As a very first application, the exercise reveals similarities and differences between these different settings. However, for inferring policy-relevant information, deeper analyses, also using more complex ABM would be needed. Yet, the structure of possible conclusions from such an analysis was laid out: for example, recognising bottlenecks in the kinetic map of an ABM may inform better targeted interventions.

Future work could investigate whether and how ABa-KiTo can be (most) useful in comparing not only different scenarios, but also different models on a similar topic. As such models will probably have different internal mechanisms, they may be hard to compare from a micro-level perspective. However, by examining their kinetic pictures, similarities and differences in structures of their state spaces could provide valuable insights into the system underlying the models and in particular into their emergent phenomena.

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A ABRam-BG

This appendix provides the details on the processes behind Figure 1.

A.1 Opinion Dynamics

At the beginning of each time step, agents' beliefs can switch from 0 to 1 stochastically following either a Voter model or Majority rule dynamics, which are two of the most studied mechanisms in opinion dynamics (5). Note that farms with opinion $\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} = 1$ are considered stubborn, they will not change their opinion to $\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} = 0$, i.e. once a farm invests in green capital, it will not revert (or begin) to invest in brown capital. The opinion dynamics process is the only source of randomness in the model. We present briefly the two opinion models that we consider for this article.

Voter Dynamics Here, agents engage in pairwise interactions: a randomly selected agent adopts the opinion of a randomly chosen neighbour. We assume that at the beginning of each time step t , $\ell \in \mathbb{N}$ random farms interact. As we assume that agents that do care will not revert to $\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} = 0$, we can describe the opinion dynamics as follows.

$$\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} = \begin{cases} \mathcal{O}_{t-1}^{(j)} & \text{if } \mathcal{O}_{t-1}^{(j)} = 1 \text{ where } j \in \mathcal{N}_i \\ \mathcal{O}_{t-1}^{(i)} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where, at each time step t , ℓ randomly selected agents choose a neighbour from their neighbourhood \mathcal{N}_i . To be precise, the imitation step is carried out for ℓ agents one after the other, so that each agent sees the most recent state of all neighbours (i.e., possibly after an earlier update in the same time step).

Majority Rule We assume that agents meet at random in a space shaped by their social life (13). At each time step t , when a group of ℓ random agents meet and discuss, the agents with opinion $\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} = 0$ update their beliefs to match the beliefs of the majority (5).

For a group $G_\ell = \{1, \dots, \ell\}$, of ℓ random agents, we define the average belief of the group at time t ,

$$\hat{\mathcal{O}}_t = \frac{1}{r} \sum_{j \in G_r} \mathcal{O}_t^{(j)}.$$

So at each time step t , for every farm in the discussion group, the beliefs are updated as follows:

$$\mathcal{O}_{t+1}^{(k)} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{when } \hat{\mathcal{O}}_t > 1/2 \\ \mathcal{O}_t^{(k)} & \text{when } \hat{\mathcal{O}}_t \leq 1/2 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

This means that if the majority's belief is $\mathcal{O}_t = 0$, all the discussion group's farms keep their previous belief.

The stochastic process These interaction processes yield $X_t = x \in \{0, 1, \dots, \ell\}$ **new green farms**, with probability $\mathbb{P}(X_t = x \mid \mathcal{G}_{t-1})$, where $\mathcal{G}_{t-1} = \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} X(s)$ is the total number of green farms at time step $t-1$. The opinion dynamics process influences the farms' investment behaviour, affecting the outcome of a green transition, as the new X_t green farms change their investment allocation into green capital. Consequently, every generation X_t of new green farms differs from the others in their accumulated brown and green capitals, introducing heterogeneity that emerges over time in the system.

A.2 Economic process

The underlying deterministic economic process in the ABM corresponds to a simple Ramsey growth model. The process is determined by the capital holding of the agents and experiences feedback in terms of directed technical progress.

Capital The capital(s) of agent i evolve(s) according to

$$B_{t+1}^{(i)} = (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)} + I_{\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)}=0}^{(i)} \quad \text{and/or} \quad G_{t+1}^{(i)} = (1 - \delta)G_t^{(i)} + I_{\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)}=1}^{(i)}, \quad (11)$$

where $0 < \delta < 1$ is the capital depreciation rate, and $I_{\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)}}^{(i)}$ is the investment of agent i in the respective capital stock according to her beliefs.

Investment Each agent either invests in green or brown capital depending on her opinion $\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)}$. The agent investment is derived from an intertemporal utility optimisation with discount factor $\rho \geq 0$ (for more detail see 10), the investment is given by

$$I_{\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)}}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{1 + \alpha\rho} \left(\rho\alpha P_{K_t}^{(i)} - (1 - \delta)K_t^{(i)} \right), \quad (12)$$

where $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$ is the capital output elasticity, $K_t^{(i)} = B_t^{(i)} + G_t^{(i)}$ is the total capital holding of the agent, and $P_{K_t}^{(i)}$ is the agent's total production.

Production Agents produce a single output from their capital and labour. Agent i 's output from the green production process is $P_{G_t}^{(i)}$ given by

$$P_{G_t}^{(i)} = (G_t^{(i)})^\alpha (\gamma_t g_t^{(i)})^{1-\alpha}, \quad (13)$$

where $g_t^{(i)}$ is the agent's green labour and γ_t the level of technological progress of the green production process, and analogously for the brown production process. The agents labour $L_t^{(i)} = g_t^{(i)} + b_t^{(i)}$ is set to $L_t^{(i)} = 1$ for simplicity. When agent i holds both capitals, she allocates her labour such that it maximises her total production (for details see (11)).

The total production output $P_{K_t}^{(i)}$ of agent i is given by the sum of both of her productions

$$P_{K_t}^{(i)} = P_{G_t}^{(i)} + P_{B_t}^{(i)}. \quad (14)$$

Technical progress measures the system's technological levels that augment the farms' production. It evolves with the systems' respective capital stocks, representing a form of learning by doing:

$$\gamma_{t+1} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N G_{t+1}^{(j)}}{\sum_{j=1}^N G_t^{(j)}} \gamma_t = \frac{G_{t+1}}{G_t} \gamma_t \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_{t+1} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N B_{t+1}^{(j)}}{\sum_{j=1}^N B_t^{(j)}} \beta_t = \frac{B_{t+1}}{B_t} \beta_t \quad (15)$$

where B_t and G_t are the economy's total brown and green capital respectively.

B Correlation Analysis

This section presents the results of the correlation analysis between the χ -function of the ABM dynamics and all 12 macro variables of the ABM. We disregard CO_2 emissions because they are directly linked with the total brown production and we consider the idealistic scenario in which green output does not produce emissions (for more detail see ABRam-BG ODD protocol (9)). A second data set of ABM simulations is used here to also validate the χ -values learned by the neural network. We compute the Spearman coefficient and mutual information kernel density estimation (MI-KDE).

Results of the correlation analysis for Scenario 1, that is, 3 agents interact per time step through voter dynamics in a fully connected network, are given in Table 5 in the main text.

B.1 Correlation analysis for Scenario 2

Correlations for the 12 macro variables with the χ -function when 3 agents interact per time step through voter dynamics on a small-world network are presented in Table 7.

B.2 Correlation analysis for Scenario 3

We present the correlation analysis for the 12 macro variables of the ABM dynamics when agents interact through a majority rule with group size 5 in Table 8.

Table 7: Correlation analysis of the χ -function with macro variables for Scenario 2

Variable	Spearman	MI-KDE
Total number of green farms	0.597	0.279
Total number of brown farms	-0.597	0.279
Green Output Share	0.515	0.297
Green Capital Share	0.471	0.241
Total Green Production	0.087	0.000
Total Green Capital Stock	0.081	0.000
Green Technical progress	0.068	0.000
Total Capital	0.037	0.000
Total Brown capital stock	0.033	0.000
Total Production (GDP)	0.025	0.000
Brown Technical progress	0.023	0.000
Total Brown Production	0.023	0.000

Table 8: Correlation analysis of the χ -function with macro variables of Scenario 3

Variable	Spearman	MI-KDE
Total number of green farms	0.809	0.655
Total number of brown farms	-0.809	0.655
Green Output share	0.693	0.531
Green Capital share	0.673	0.532
Total Green Production	0.344	0.000
Total Green Capital stock	0.344	0.000
Green Technical progress	0.314	0.000
Brown Technical progress	-0.192	0.140
Brown Technical progress	-0.191	0.140
Total Production (GDP)	-0.185	0.140
Total Brown capital	-0.178	0.140
Total Capital	-0.171	0.140